

Patents as Indicators of Innovative Environment

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Abstract : The main problem is that there is a very low innovation performance in Latvia. Since Latvia is a Member State of European Union, it also shall have to fulfill the set targets and to improve innovative results. Universities are one of the main performers to provide innovative capacity of country. University, industry and government need to cooperate for getting best results. The intellectual property is one of the indicators to determine innovation level in the country or organization and patents are one of the characteristics of intellectual property. The objective of the article is to determine indicators characterizing innovative environment in Latvia and influence of the development of universities on them. The methods that will be used in the article to achieve the objectives are quantitative and qualitative analysis of the literature, statistical data analysis, and graphical analysis methods.

Keywords : HEI, innovations, Latvia, patents

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